

Synthesis of some 1-Acetyl-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazoline Derivatives and their Antimicrobial Activities

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Title compounds, 1-acetyl-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazolines (3a-m), were synthesised by the reaction of hydrazine hydrate with the corresponding 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-2-propenones (1a-m) in acetic acid.

The antibacterial and antifungal activities of the compounds were tested against some gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria and fungi.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-2-propenone derivatives (chalcone) possess antibacterial and antifungal activities¹ and the pyrazolines formed by conversion of chalcone structure to a rigid ring system show similar activities^{2,3}. Therefore we have synthesised some new 1-acetyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-aryl-2-pyrazolines and investigate their antimicrobial properties against some bacteria and yeast-like fungi by using tube-dilution method.

3a; Ar=Phenyl
3b; Ar=*o*-Tolyl
3c; Ar=*p*-Tolyl
3d; Ar=*o*-Anisyl
3e; Ar=*p*-Anisyl
3f; Ar=*o*-Chlorophenyl

3g; Ar=*p*-Chlorophenyl
3h; Ar=*o*-Fluorophenyl
3i; Ar=*p*-Fluorophenyl
3j; Ar=*o*-Bromophenyl
3k; Ar=*p*-Bromophenyl
3l; Ar=2-Pyridyl
3m; Ar=4-Pyridyl

Experimental

All chemicals used of Merck made. Mps. were taken in a Thomas-Hoover apparatus in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Uv spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 160 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 457 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆ and CDCl₃) on a Brücker AC 200 (200 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Microanalyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240C instrument at the Scientific and Technical Research Council of Turkey. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-2-propenones (1a-m) : To a mixture of the aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol)

and 4-chloroacetophenone (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol and was added slowly an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (0.0128 mol) in water (6 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at 15–30°. The resulting solid crystallised from ethanol.

1-Acetyl-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-aryl-2-pyrazolines (3a-m) : Hydrazine hydrate (98% ; 0.05 ml) was added to a solution of the propenone (1a-m ; 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 5 h. The solution was then concentrated under diminished pressure and poured into ice-water. The resulting solid was crystallised from isopropanol.

Microbiology : Mueller-Hinton broth (Oxoid) and blood agar (Difco) for bacteria, Sabouraud dextrose broth (Difco) and Sabouraud dextrose agar (Difco) for fungi were used as media. The antimicrobial activities of the compounds against some gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus faecalis*), gram-negative (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) bacteria and some yeast-like fungi (*Candida albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, *C. pseudotropicalis* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*) were investigated by the tube-dilution method. The concentration of the compounds were 100, 75, 50, 37.5, 25, 12.5, 6.25, 3.12, 1.56, 0.78 and 0.39 µg ml⁻¹ respectively and the final inoculum size was 10⁻⁵–10⁻⁶ m org ml⁻¹. The minimal inhibitory concentration values of the compounds were found to be > 100 µg ml⁻¹ against all the microorganisms.

Results and Discussion

Compounds 3a-m were synthesised by refluxing 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-aryl-2-propenone derivatives (1a-m) prepared by the reaction of the corresponding aromatic aldehydes and 4-chloroacetophenone

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3b - m*

Compd.	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	ν_{\max}	δ	λ_{\max} (log ϵ) [†]
3b	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O	143-44	73	1 640 (C=O), 1 585 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 765 (1,2-disubstituted-benzene)	α 2.34 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.37 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.00 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.87 Hz), 3.89 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.91 Hz), 5.65 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.83 Hz), 6.85-7.82 (8H, m, ArH)	221 (4.23), 226 (4.14), 302 (4.40)
3c	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O	124-25	76	1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 820 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	β 2.30 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.10 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.70 Hz), 3.70 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.83 Hz), 5.55 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.72 Hz), 7.07-7.69 (8H, m, ArH)	222 (4.28), 229sh (4.16), 302 (4.41)
3d	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂	130-31	81	1 650 (C=O), 1 595 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 750 (1,2-disubstituted-benzene)	α 2.33 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 2.95 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.78 Hz), 3.77 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.80 Hz), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.67 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.67 Hz), 6.87-7.83 (8H, m, ArH)	227 (4.32), 304 (4.42)
3e	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ClN ₂ O ₂	137-38	71	1 650 (C=O), 1 585 (C=N), 825 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	α 2.15 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.10 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.80 Hz), 3.72 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.81 Hz), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.50 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.84 Hz), 6.81-7.86 (8H, m, ArH)	225 (4.34), 302 (4.40)
3f	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O	140-41	83	1 640 (C=O), 1 580 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 755 (1,2-disubstituted benzene)	α 2.35 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.07 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 5.08 Hz), 3.94 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 12.04 Hz), 5.76 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 5.05 Hz), 7.04-7.82 (8H, m, ArH)	220 (4.24), 229sh (4.12), 291 (4.40)
3g	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₂ O	106-07	80	1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	β 2.40 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.08 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.86 Hz), 3.72 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.91 Hz), 5.55 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.82 Hz), 7.12-7.70 (8H, m, ArH)	223 (4.26), 230sh (4.14), 289 (4.45)
3h	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O	126-27	79	1 655 (C=O), 1 585 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted benzene), 760 (1,2-disubstituted-benzene)	β 2.43 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.11 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 5.12 Hz), 3.75 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.93 Hz), 5.80 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 5.08 Hz), 7.01-7.70 (8H, m, ArH)	216sh (4.13), 229 (4.11), 291 (4.41)
3i	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O	100-01	84	1 650 (C=O), 1 585 (C=N), 825 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	β 2.40 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.10 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.75 Hz), 3.72 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.85 Hz), 5.57 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.76 Hz), 7.00-7.70 (8H, m, ArH)	218 (4.18), 230 (4.13), 293 (4.45)
3j	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrClN ₂ O	117-18	69	1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 775 (1,2-disubstituted-benzene)	β 2.40 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.08 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.87 Hz), 3.73 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.89 Hz), 5.54 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.85 Hz), 7.06-7.69 (8H, m, ArH)	220 (4.32), 295 (4.38)
3k	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ BrClN ₂ O	121-22	85	1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C=N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene)	β 2.40 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.08 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.87 Hz), 3.72 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.89 Hz), 5.53 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.85 Hz), 7.00-7.70 (8H, m, ArH)	223 (4.29), 292 (4.34)

(Table 1 contd.)

(Table 1 contd.)

3l	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O	164 - 65	63	1 640 (C=O), 1 595 (C-N), 835 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 760 (1,2-disubstituted-benzene)	α 2.42 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.10 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.85 Hz), 3.75 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.85 Hz), 5.65 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.83 Hz), 7.23 - 8.45 (8H, m, ArH)	212 (3.2), 265 (4.15)
3m	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O	252 - 53	65	1 640 (C=O), 1 590 (C-N), 830 (1,4-disubstituted-benzene), 790 (1,2-disubstituted-benzene)	2.41 (3H, s, COCH ₃), 3.12 (1H, dd, H _A , J _{AB} 4.86 Hz), 3.69 (1H, dd, H _B , J _{BX} 11.90 Hz), 5.60 (1H, dd, H _X , J _{XA} 4.83 Hz), 7.19 - 8.35 (8H, m, ArH)	210 (3.91), 261 (4.04)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

**In MeOH. ^aIn DMSO-d₆. ^bIn CDCl₃.

with excess hydrazine hydrate (2) in glacial acetic acid.

1-Acetyl-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazoline derivatives can be prepared by using two different methods. In the first method, 3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazoline derivatives are obtained by refluxing chalcone compounds (1a-m) with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol⁵⁻¹⁰ or pyridine. Then these compounds are acetylated with acetic acid^{5,8,9} or acetic anhydride/pyridine^{7,8}. In the second method, 1-acetyl-3,5-diaryl-2-pyrazolines are formed by the reaction of chalcone derivatives with hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid^{5-7,9-11}. In this study, we preferred the second method, because it was an one-step reaction. Compound 3a was synthesised by the reported method¹². Since antimicrobial properties of this compound was not reported in that work, we have tested its activity.

The structure of the compounds are in accordance with their chemical and spectral data (Table 1). The uv spectra of the pyrazolines show intensive bands in the regions 300 and 220 nm which reflect structural assignment^{9,10,12,13}. In the ir spectra, $\nu_{C=O}$ stretching, ν_{C-H} and $\nu_{C=C}$ bending vibrations are at the expected values. Moreover $\nu_{C=N}$ stretching bands are seen in the region 1 600 cm⁻¹, belonging to the pyrazoline ring^{9,10,12,14}. In the ¹H nmr spectra, the acetyl protons are seen at δ 2.35 and these values are accordance with the reported data¹³. The H_A and H_B protons of the pyrazoline ring are discernible in the regions δ 2.95 - 3.11 and 3.70 - 3.94 as double doublets respectively. The H_X proton is observed at δ 5.65 as double doublets (J_{AB} 4.70 - 5.12 Hz,

J_{BX} 11.80 - 12.04 Hz, J_{XA} 4.67 - 5.03 Hz)^{9,15}. The results of elementary analyses gave further support to the structure.

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